

Impact of posture and writing surface on handwriting characteristics

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Abstract

Handwriting is the technique of writing using any writing instrument i.e. pen, pencil. The characteristics of handwriting are unique in every individual. The main characteristics are classified in two types i.e. class characteristics and individual characteristics. Class characteristics are common in a group of individuals with some or the other similarity like sex, region, etc. Individual characteristics are the unique features of an individual's handwriting. This research aims to study the variations in handwriting on different writing surfaces and postures. A total of 150 samples were collected by 25 candidates between the age of 18-25 on two surfaces i.e. smooth surface (clipboard) and a rough surface (the irregular side of the clipboard). The collected samples were analysed for variations and the observations were noted. The study concluded that there were significant variations in the samples but the writing surface played a bigger role than posture.

Keywords: *Forensic Science, Handwriting Examination, Variations, Individual characteristics, Class Characteristics.*

Introduction

As we know, the handwriting of every individual is unique and is humanly impossible to replicate thus, laying the foundation of this study. Handwriting is a motor skill and depends on various factors like age of the writer, gender of the writer, physical wellbeing, environmental conditions, knowledge of the language, education, etc.

The characteristics of handwriting are classified in two types:

Class characteristics: found common in a group of individuals that have some or the other similarity.

Individual characteristics: unique features of an individual's handwriting that differentiate them from others. ^[1]

Everyone's handwriting shows some natural variations that are dependent on various factors such as mood of the writer, age, physical wellbeing, etc. The writing instrument, writing surface and the posture of the person while writing also contributes to the variations in an individual's handwriting. Handwriting analysis can be very crucial in forensic science. As we are aware of the uniqueness in the handwriting it can be used as a means of individual identification. ^[2]

Forensic analysis of the handwriting found on an unusual surface can be much more difficult for the experts as the writing surface can hinder a person's handwriting and cause unintentional variation hence making it difficult to identify the writer. In some cases, it is deliberately done for disguising the handwriting to conceal the identity of the writer making it even more challenging for the experts to come to any conclusions. ^[3]

Handwriting characteristics are also influenced by the bodily position of the writer while writing. **Huber and Hendrick**^[19] also mentioned in their book about a case study presented by the Grant 1974, in which the handwriting of the individual written in an uncomfortable position is often distorted and has significant differences. Sciacca et.al conducted a study where they collected samples from people in four different positions: sitting, standing, kneeling, and lying. They concluded that the variation is very high in the samples collected while kneeling and laying prone.^[4]

In criminal investigations, handwriting analysis is used very often to link a person to a crime, eliminate suspects e.g. Ransome letters, threat letters, etc are analysed for identifying the writer. Handwriting evidence is admissible in the court of law if the person handling it is an expert in handwriting analysis and it is somewhat linked to the case.

Some features used for the comparison of handwriting are:

- **Slant:** It is defined as the tilt in the handwriting that can be horizontal or vertical. It is of three types i.e. straight or upright, left, right.
- **Pen Pressure:** this characteristic is completely dependent on the writer. It is basically the pen handling technique that is unique in every individual.
- **Pen Lifts:** it refers to how often the writing instrument i.e. pen or pencil is lifted while writing a sample. This characteristic is completely writer dependent. Hence, making it unique.
- **Line Quality:** refers to the smoothness and continuity of lines in strokes formation. It is used to measure how fluent the writer is.
- **Size:** this is the size of the words in a sample. This remains constant if the writer is same if the writing is not disguised.

Overall, handwriting analysis can be considered an important technique in the field of forensic science.^[5]

Materials and Methodology

In this study, 25 candidates between the age of 18-25 provided the samples on 2 surfaces i.e. regular surface and irregular surface in 3 different postures i.e. sitting, standing and walking. Writing surface and writing instruments provided to the writers were constant throughout the process of sample collection with writing surface being a clipboard as the regular surface and the unpolished side of the same clipboard as the irregular, writing instrument being a blue gel pen.

Using the above stated equipment, 25 individuals irrespective of their gender provided us with 6 samples each, making it a total of 150 samples. Then, the samples were analysed for variations.

The characteristics that were common in most of the samples were used to analyse the variation. The characteristics being slant, line quality, size, pen pressure and pen lifts.

The variations were measured on a scale of 0-1, with 0 being negligible to no variations at all and 1 being the significant variations.

Table 1: Number of samples.

Surface/ Posture	Sitting	Standing	Walking	
Regular Surface	25	25	25	
Irregular Surface	25	25	25	
Total	50	50	50	150

The samples were compared to each other thrice during the analysis.

Firstly, samples collected on regular surfaces in all three postures were compared and analysed to each other for similarities and differences in the variations (if any). A total of 75 samples were compared to each other.

Similarly, samples collected on irregular surfaces in all three postures were analysed to each other for the similarities and differences in the variations (if any). Total 75 samples were compared to each other .

Lastly, samples collected on both regular and irregular surfaces were compared and analysed for the similarities and differences in variations (if any). 150 samples were compared to each other.

Results

Slant: this is one such characteristic that had very less variation. Irrespective of posture and writing surface this characteristic remained constant in most of the samples.

Pen Pressure: this characteristic had significant changes with respect to the posture and writing surface. The pen pressure on irregular surface has been lighter as compared to regular surface.

Pen Lifts: this characteristic also had significant variation in it. These were present on samples collected on both the surfaces as well as in all 3 postures. This denoted the unfamiliarity while writing on different postures.

Line Quality: this characteristics showed variation, samples collected on irregular surface had disturbed line quality as compared to the samples collected on regular surface. Similarly samples collected while standing and walking also had somewhat disturbed line quality.

Size: the letter size also changed with postures and writing surfaces. The size of letters on samples collected in sitting and standing postures were mostly constant whereas, the samples collected while walking had a significant change in the size in most of the samples.

Conclusions

We can conclude that handwriting characteristics of an individual are dependent on the posture of the writer at the time of writing and the writing surface the person is writing on. There were very minimal variations in sitting posture when smooth surface was used as one is habitual of the same but had significant variations when on the very same surface the posture of the writer was different.

Whereas, for irregular surfaces it is different as the surface itself tends to create some inconsistencies in the handwriting characteristics and along with the posture aspect, the variations are much more and more noticeable

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